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Beta-catenin is an immune regulator.

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Beta-catenin functions in a pathway that includes APC which restricts transformation through traditionally understood growth control and tumor suppression pathways focused on cycling. We demonstrate here that beta-catenin is an immune regulator: we observed collapse of immune regulatory functions in human cells lacking beta-catenin similar to cells of the thymus lacking the major described autoimmune regulator, AIRE. Loss of function analysis demonstrated the tumor suppressor-like molecule has a dominant function in fine control of self non-self recognition through activation of tissue-restricted antigens, most likely to restrict metastasis to distant organ sites.

1 **Results**

2 Class I MHC and antigen presentation machinery

- 3 1. Ctnnb1 depletion results in activation of TRIM22 and Psmb8, Ube2l6 and B2M.
4 a. Ube2l6
5 2. HLA-B, HLA-C
6 3. Identity associated with antigen presentation and self non-self: Sp100 and Sp110
7

8 Interferon signaling

- 9 4. Ctnnb1 depletion results in activation of interferon reporter genes Mx1 and Mx2 and
10 nearly all major ISGs.

11 Control of thymic negative selection for regulation of metastasis.

- 12 5. Ctnnb1 controls expression of organ-specific TRA.

13 Fgg

14 Fgb

15 Alb

16 Itih

- 17 6. Ctnnb1 depletion results in loss of Igdcc3.

18 Immunologic privilege and senescence

- 19 7. Ctnnb1 controls Ifi27l2 but not Ifi27l1.

20 Exhaustion receptors

- 21 8. Havcr1 activation
22 9. Batf2 activation

23 Endogenous anti-tumor signaling

- 24 10. CIDEC activation
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